

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Clustering of multiple-event online sound collections with the codebook approach

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*What's Montague? It is nor hand, nor foot,
Nor arm, nor face, nor any other part
Belonging to a man. O, be some other name!
What's in a name? That which we call a rose
By any other name would smell as sweet (...)*

William Shakespeare, *Romeo and Juliet*

*(...) But we talk about it as we do about pieces in chess when we are stating the
rules of the game, not describing their physical properties.*

The question "What is a word really?" is analogous to "What is a piece in chess?"

Ludwig Wittgenstein, *Philosophical Investigations*

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Abstract

In massive online audio databases such as Freesound, automatic methods to encode, process, compare and organize the content are relevant topics of research. For instance, a properly organized presentation of these audio collections can improve the user experience when browsing for sounds. When dealing with collections of diverse audio content, some items can contain multiple sonic events. This multi-event audio clips might be challenging to numerically encode in a concise yet representative manner. However, these numerical representations are essential in order to proceed with further computation of the signal.

This multiple-event audio clips might be misrepresented by statistical aggregation methods such as computing the mean over the features; in this regard, techniques that retain the elemental blocks of a given signal can be potentially beneficial.

This thesis aims to explore the contribution of the codebook approach to the clustering of large collections of multiple-event audio content. The codebook approach might allow to automatically obtain "acoustic words", which are discrete partitions of the feature space that could be roughly representative of the underlying acoustic events present in the original sounds. These "acoustic words" can be understood and processed analogous to natural language words, thus giving access to the use of varied Natural Language Processing techniques, such as Bag-of-Words, TF-IDF or neural network word embeddings. We believe that this approach could help to improve the similarity assessment between multi-event audio clips, and potentially increase the accuracy on an ulterior clustering stage. In future works, this text analogy might also empower interesting artistic research.

In order to experiment with the presented concepts, a corresponding end-to-end processing pipeline has been implemented. Freesound Datasets and a brand new custom dataset of acoustic scenes have been employed to perform the experiments. The codebase and the custom dataset are both delivered in the accompanying Github project (<https://github.com/lluissuros/codebook-approach>). The experiments results are reported, discussed and expanded with ideas for future work.

Keywords: audio, clustering, codebook, vector quantization, NLP

Chapter 1

Introduction

Digital multimedia became mainstream in the 90s, and gradually replaced analog-based mediums within telecommunications, artistic production, record and cinema industries or broadcasting. Digital multimedia could be copied inexpensively and without quality loss, processed with computers, compressed, saved in tiny memory chips and hard drives. Later, since the advent of the internet, humans have been able to upload, download, stream and share their digital multimedia content online. The expanding amount of material available nowadays is stored in massive online multimedia databases and can include audio, speech, text, image, video, games and their combinations. This online collections are accessed through a wide variety of devices and software interfaces. This has generated a broad range of challenges; for example, improving information storage and access, organizing huge collections, optimising the information retrieval upon users requests, developing recommendation systems, and many more. At the same time, the massive amounts of available content and metadata, the increasing computing power and the progressive sophistication of the state-of-the-art machine learning solutions have engendered new ways of generating knowledge and insights, creating businesses, enhancing academic research, and ultimately empowering end users.

Since sound and music are our particular concern, large online sound collections present the same range of aforementioned challenges and opportunities. Although

the background and experiments provided in this thesis could be applied to other online sound databases, our progress will develop under the Freesound platform.

Freesound (<https://freesound.org>) is a website that hosts a large database of diverse audio clips released under Creative Commons licenses that facilitate their reuse. It is currently developed and maintained by the Music Technology Group at the Pompeu Fabra University (UPF). Freesound allows users to upload any type of sonic content, of any length, creating a very diverse database. This diversity includes single instruments (synthesizers, guitars, drums...), speech, field recordings (nature, urban, industrial, animals, rooms, ambiences), audio samples, special effects, music excerpts (world music, experimental, rock, jazz...) and so on.

In addition to sharing audio content, users can comment, tag, rate, label and provide text descriptions to sounds, which enable the use of a traditional text-based search engine. However, this metadata can be incomplete, misleading or simply missing. Different terms might be used to describe the same concepts. Users might be biased, forgetful, ambiguous, confused, inexperienced, untrustworthy. The huge size of the sound database (at the moment about 400k sounds, and daily growing) makes it a daunting (if not impossible) task to manually annotate all the collection.

Therefore, automatic methods that are able to process the audio content itself can provide beneficial alternatives in browsing, exploring and retrieving sounds. These automatic methods could be used to extract new and consistent metadata from the content itself, compute similarities between sounds, or group similar sounds together using clustering. Clustering is a set of techniques aiming at grouping together similar elements, according to a certain definition of similarity. Clustering techniques can be executed without human supervision, so they can be effective on the task of automatically organizing and classifying sound collections.

As an example, when a user submits the 'dog' search query to the Freesound search engine, the system returns a wide variety of sounds involving different concepts. Big and small dogs barking, howls, aggressive dogs, field recordings where a dog and his owner walk in the park, or even dog toys. Figure 1 shows a snapshot of this case.

The user could be potentially looking for any of the mentioned sound categories. In this regard, a possible strategy would be to automatically cluster (group) the sounds into meaningful sub-topics and present them to the user at once. Figure 2 presents an interesting solution from Google image search, where these potential groups are offered to the user.

Figure 1: Top results for the "dog" search query in Freesound <https://freesound.org/search/?q=dog>. Just within these few examples we can find a dog toy recording, aggressive dogs, barks, or a pack of dogs. The underlying sound in each example might be significantly different from the others. A glimpse on the tag cloud in the right side illustrates the wide diversity of the retrieved content.

Depending on the underlying sounds, this clustering techniques might require different processing strategies. Specifically, we are interested in researching on how to deal with collections of multiple-event sounds, such as field recordings, drum patterns, musical excerpts, acoustic scenes, etc.

In this thesis, we will explore the codebook approach, under the hypothesis that it can contribute positively to clustering collections of sounds that contain multiple events. In short, the codebook approach could contribute in finding "acoustic words", which could correspond to the underlying acoustic events of the original sounds. This "acoustic words" can be understood and processed as analog to nat-

Figure 2: Google search image engine has recently introduced a section with sub-topics related to an ambiguous search query

ural language words. We will present a codebase which implements these concepts and the results of the experiments will be discussed.

Following this introduction, the State of the Art will be reviewed in the next section. Next, methodology will be described in chapter 3, paying special attention to the processing pipeline specifications and the datasets used. After, obtained results will be explained in chapter 4. Finally, a discussion on the results will be presented, along with some ideas for future research.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

The rise of the internet has empowered billions of humans to upload, download, stream and share their digital multimedia content online. Users search this multimedia data in their websites of choice and expect to find satisfying results quickly, usually making use of text-based search engines. The expanding amount of material available nowadays is stored in massive multimedia databases, and can include audio, speech, text, image, video and their combinations. This produces a manifold of technical problems, for example how to store and organize this data efficiently or how to precisely respond to diverse user requests. Figure 3 is provided as an illustrative summarization of this emerging challenges.

Without the support of automated tools, researchers or employees would have to go through a monumental volume of multimedia instances, annotating, describing and categorizing each single item. This manual process is extremely time-consuming, repetitive, prone to subjectivity biases and errors. In many cases, an exhaustive annotation of these multimedia collections might just be practically impossible [1][2][3]. Therefore, research on automatic, unsupervised methods dealing with multimedia content has become a highly relevant topic of research.

Furthermore, in order to provide solutions such as pattern recognition, content-based retrieval or similarity search in these large datasets, multimedia data will need to be encoded and categorized in some way. For example, each specific gesture, event,

image or sound needs to be described and classified, in order to relate them to similar instances, and to finally be delivered to a potentially interested user.

In this State of the Art section, unnecessary technicalities will be avoided, while offering at the same time a satisfactory background to understand the Methodology and Results chapters. The curious reader is welcome to delve into the provided bibliography for further technical insight. The forthcoming sections build on each other conceptually, and cross references are provided. In the first section, the Sound and Music Computing context relative to this thesis is introduced.

Figure 3: <https://dilbert.com>

2.1 Sound Retrieval

This section aims to offer a contextual review about sound retrieval, specially over large online audio databases. The Freesound platform (<https://freesound.org>) is also presented as a practical use case for the upcoming experiments.

Additionally, a brief overview about Music Information Retrieval (MIR) and Sound and Music Computing (SMC) is presented, mentioning some of its achievements, goals, and current challenges.

2.1.1 Large Online Databases

At the time of writing, large online databases are probably the most popular way of accessing to any kind of multimedia content. Mainstream multimedia databases from companies such as Youtube, Spotify, Pandora, Soundcloud, Instagram, Facebook, Netflix and similar platforms are nowadays upon the most accessed websites worldwide.

Among these popular online databases, some with non-lucrative goals such as Looperman (<https://www.looperman.com>) or Freesound (<https://freesound.org>) aim at facilitating the sharing and reuse of content by adopting free, easy-to-use copyright licenses such as Creative Commons [4].

At the same time, the content on these platforms can also benefit researchers and application developers on an extensive range of Sound and Music Computing (SMC) tasks, which in the long run might provide results that can be applied back as improvements on these platforms. A good example of this virtuous circle is the upcoming release of the FSD which is explained in section 2.1.5.

2.1.2 MIR and SMC

Multiple different definitions can be found about Music Information Retrieval (MIR) since the field emerged in the 90s and consolidated in the early 2000s. Influential authors stress the focus on the extraction, analysis and use of musical information,

aimed to connect these numerical descriptors with the corresponding human mental perceptions, thanks to the development of increasingly symbolic categories. Finally, powered by the increasing availability of multimodal data and smarter algorithms, the "age of context-awareness" blossomed, and the processing of contextual data regarding music and users (for example, cultural data or users metadata and biography) was focused on. Additionally, a hypothetical fourth "age of creative systems" is devised, where the accumulated knowledge is applied into creative or generative systems, and art and music production integrate the advances of the research.

Sound and Music Computing (SMC) could be considered as a more general field which not only includes music, but also sound or speech processing. Within this thesis, SMC acronym will be used to designate the broader background of audio processing (including speech, sound, and music), while MIR will be used for more music-specific context. MIR and SMC share multiple interconnected areas of research (as an example, the recently mentioned three "ages" of MIR would be perfectly applicable to SMC).

In summary, Sound and Music Computing science is the context where this present thesis operates. The upcoming sections of this State of the Art will gradually deepen into the relevant background for this specific work. For a broader perspective on MIR field, the reader is welcomed to go through the previously mentioned [5], [6] or the comprehensive survey on MIR by Emilia Gomez *et al* [7].

2.1.3 Datasets

A dataset is a collection of data. It can consist of database tables, or collections of files or documents. It is presented as an entity and normally it is accessed from a single entry point. This datasets can have very restrictive access such as those hosted by private companies or governments, while others might be accessed openly and for free. In this regard, an interesting movement is Open Data, which is aligned with the open-source idea of free availability for use without restrictions of copyright or control mechanisms [8] [9].

In the context of data science, pattern recognition, machine learning and SMC, datasets are essential because most of the algorithms often need to be trained over massive amounts of data to exhibit better performance results. In his well known paper "The unreasonable effectiveness of data", Halevy *et al* explain how the increase in orders of magnitude on the training examples (i.e from millions to trillions of examples) can drive the same algorithm to outperform its performance in certain tasks, even if the data is not so well curated as in the smaller dataset [10]. Nevertheless, other activities will need to deal with carefully annotated data. Some datasets have become popular references in audiovisual research, as they provide a way to compare the performance of different algorithms over exactly the same task. Some of this notorious datasets in image recognition are the classical Iris Dataset and the MNIST database, or more recently the ImageNet database [11] [12] [13]. Regarding sound and music, some relevant examples are the Million Song Dataset, the GTZAN [14] [15], AudioSet Dataset [16], Urban Sound Dataset [17] and the Freesound Dataset [18].

2.1.4 Freesound

As it currently presents itself on its welcome page www.freesound.org, Freesound hosts "a collaborative database of Creative Commons Licensed sounds". It was created and has been maintained at the MTG (Music Technology Group) in UPF (Universitat Pompeu Fabra) from Barcelona. The project started in 2005 as a web application where users could share sound recordings. Since then, it has been widely adopted by sound artists, sound designers, application developers and researchers [4].

Freesound offers an interesting variety of research resources, as sketched in Figure 5. On the front end, users can browse sounds through a typical text search interface, or explore different sounds by similarity. Users can also label, rate and comment the uploaded sounds, allowing the community to expand and enrich to collection. This social interactions between users have also been proved useful in SMC research, like some of the research carried on by Sergio Oramas, where he presented audio

recommendation systems based on the analysis of textual information or the social structure of the users [19] [20]. A programmatic access to the sound database, similarity engine and feature extraction is provided by means of a REST API. Within this interface, software developers can perform a variety of tasks such as downloading audio content and features in order to build third party applications.

Both Front End and API access have been used thoroughly within the development on this thesis, in ways that will be gradually disclosed in the upcoming chapters.

Figure 5: Freesound architecture. Some of the building blocks are outlined here. [4]

2.1.5 Freesound Dataset (FSD)

As previously indicated, researchers have been developing multiple tools and relevant resources under the Freesound umbrella. One of the latest additions to the SMC community is the Freesound Dataset (FSD), which is still an ongoing project with no official release yet [18]. As will be described in chapters 3 and 4, FSD datasets have been used as dataset for some experiments within this thesis.

FSD is a large scale, open dataset made up of Freesound content, and organised according to the AudioSetOntology (<https://research.google.com/audioset>) [16],

which is a hierarchical taxonomy of sound-related categories (see section 2.2.2 for more details). Each sound item in FSD has been annotated by humans, crowd-sourced by means of the Freesound Annotator web platform (<https://annotator.freesound.org>), whose curation principles are outlined in [21]. More details about the FSD version used in this thesis will be disclosed in chapter 3.2.1.

FSD is appropriate for evaluating our hypothesis, since it contains a wide variety of sounds clips, uploaded by many different users; it has the characteristics of an online sound collection. Additionally, since these sounds are labeled according to a specific ontology, they can be used as a ground truth for machine learning tasks. The FSD allows to test our research methodology approach and check the correspondence between the obtained results and the original labels.

2.2 Audio Representation

In vast databases such as Freesound, with hundreds of thousands of available sounds, it is not practical to annotate each individual sound manually. The possibility to algorithmically extract and process information from the audio itself becomes very valuable. When the content itself is used as the source material for obtaining numerical representations, the approach is denominated as *content-based*, in opposition to *context-based* approach which deals with external metadata [22].

In order to enable automatic methods based on the audio content itself, a numerical representation of this content must be obtained in a preliminary step. With this numerical representations, it is possible to compare items, define and assess similarity and organize collections. In audiovisual research, these numerical representations are called *features* and constitute the building blocks for any kind of content-based computational process. Within this thesis, only content-based features will be used, as we are interested in developing automatic methods that can function without the need of external metadata. This section intends to provide contextual background on audio representation and the techniques that are related to the presented work.

2.2.1 Audio Features

When computing over digital audio, there will be a preliminary step where some features are extracted. We refer to this step as *feature extraction*, which is the process of converting an audio signal into numerical data that carry characteristic information about the original signal. Since sound and music develop over time, the typical feature extraction process would require to first divide the signal into smaller, manageable sections which are called *frames*. The frame size might change, depending upon the application and the feature to be extracted (as an example, some features would work with frame size of less than 50 milliseconds, and others might require more than one second). The term *feature vector* is used to designate a list of features, for example the ones describing a single frame. After this process, usually an audio clip will be represented as a time series of feature vectors. This series of feature vectors will be the basis on further SMC work such as similarity assessment, classification, pattern recognition or machine learning.

In the past decades many different categories of features have been successfully employed to infer music similarity and to classify sound and music. In MIR literature, *low-level* to *high-level* terminology is used to designate different levels of abstraction. Low-level refers to practical, mathematical and closer to the signal features. High-level refers to more semantic and abstract features. Figure 6 provides a general view on feature types. The *semantic gap* stamped on the figure refers to the limitations presented particularly by low-level features to satisfactorily represent human understanding [5]. This semantic gap could be originated on the multiplicity of external factors that influence humans on music understanding, such as musical education, cultural background or personal taste. A complementary overview on the semantic gap is offered in Figure 7. Although the semantic gap has been narrowed down with the advent of mid-level and higher-level descriptors [23], this condition should not be overlooked when dealing with audio features.

Figure 6: Low-level to high-level features, and the *semantic gap* between them. The semantic gap stamped on the figure refers to the limitations presented particularly by low-level features to satisfactorily represent human understanding [5]

Figure 7: Music Information feature types and the semantic gap, according to [23]

Low level features

Within MIR literature, *low-level* terminology is used because of that proximity to the physical encoding, and normally refer to numerical representations of properties

related amplitude, temporal changes, frequency, to the spectral shape, etc [6]. Even if these descriptors have little meaning to users, they can be easily exploited by computer systems. As explained by Schedl *et al* in their 2014 book [7], low-level descriptors are usually related to loudness and timbre. They should provide a proper representation of the studied sound, be deterministic and robust.

Figure 8: Diagram for low-level feature extraction [7]

Low-level features are extracted from small segments or *frames* of the audio file, and normally presented as feature vectors to become the basis of higher-level processing. Therefore, they have a great influence on the overall performance of the final application. The frame size might vary depending on the feature extractor and the application requirements. As a guideline, Freesound similarity search uses a frame size of 2048 samples for the low-level namespace, while for the tonal namespace the frame size is 4096 (for a sampling rate of 44100Hz, which means 2048 samples are about 45 milliseconds). In the case of Freesound, the Essentia library is used to perform the feature extraction (https://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/freesound_extractor.html) [24]. Figure 8 depicts a general diagram for low-level feature extraction.

It is outside of the scope of this thesis to explain the variety of popular low-level descriptors available for SMC. The curious reader will find a thorough introduction in the second chapter of the MIR book by Emilia Gomez *et al* [7]. Some worth mentioning examples are *Zero Crossing Rate*, energy, loudness, *sharpness*, *spectral*

centroid or *spectral flux*. However, to finish this section, MFCCs will be reviewed, a particular case of low-level features which is widely popular in SMC and that it will be also used in this thesis.

Mel-Frequency Cepstrum Coefficients (MFCCs) have been used up until the present date to represent in a compact way (with 13 coefficients typically) a signal spectrum. Whilst MFCCs were initially developed to represent the human vocal tract and hearing system in the context of speech recognition (see Rabiner and Schafer [25]), they perform solidly as timbre, pitch invariant descriptors and have been used on many MIR and SMC tasks outside of speech recognition. The technical implementation can be found in seminal works such as Logan [26], and the block diagram (also borrowed from [7]) is offered in Figure 9 for a general view. In several SMC papers, MFCCs are still offered as a baseline to compare against new high-level methods. MFCCs have been used in a broad range of applications such as musical genre classification, instrument classification, audio similarity measures or timbral models [26], [27], [28], [29], and [30].

Figure 9: MFCC block diagram [7]

High-level features

As hinted in the previous chapter (see Figure 7), low-level features are not enough to tackle the diverse research challenges that MIR researchers have attempted to solve. Tasks such as classification, recommendation, similarity assessment or music transcription demanded new features that helped to progressively shorten the semantic gap [31], providing more human-like, domain-knowledge informed numerical descriptions of the underlying audio content. As an example, AudioCommons project presented high-level features designed as timbral attributes such as Hardness, Depth, Brightness, Warmth, Roughness, Sharpness, Boominess, and Reverberation [27]. Even though these are still numerical attributes, they are clearly inspired after human-like subjective experience, and they were actually selected after being the most searched in Freesound.

As explained by Herrera in his "age of semantics" chapter [6], dealing with categories created and manipulated by humans will imply addressing *semantics*. This descriptors would need to convey a defined "meaning" that is more aligned with the subjective experience of the musical content, and not necessarily associated with the audio signal properties. This semantic descriptors are denominated in the MIR literature as *high-level* features.

High-level features are still being developed to date, with increasingly sophisticated methods which might include musical and sound domain knowledge, cognitive science and auditory perception [32], and lately the irruption of the so-called machine learning methods, with a special relevance on deep learning methods [33]. These deep-learned features might also allow transfer learning, which means that pre-trained models can be used in diverse tasks besides its original problem, serving as general-purpose descriptors, such as the experiments presented by Choi *et al* in [34], where a neural network was trained for music tagging and then transferred to other music-related classification and regression tasks.

Deep Learned Features

Deep learning is an umbrella term for a subset of machine learning techniques, based on artificial neural networks with several layers. It is outside the scope of this State of the Art section to get into details about the wide range of techniques that have proved successful within the Sound And Music Computing domain, but it is necessary to provide the needed context to introduce AudioSet embeddings [35], which will be used in this thesis experiments as a high-level feature for sound representation.

Although deep neural networks are not a new concept in the machine learning field (the original Perceptron concept was already published in 1966 [36]), and specially since this last decade it has attracted a lot of academic, industrial and media attention while beating state-of-the-art performance in many pattern recognition and machine learning tasks. Several reasons explain this renewed activity, from hardware advances such as the usage of GPU, to the internet-powered data availability explosion, to the emergence of a new variety of techniques, improvements and heuristics [37]. Among the fields that have benefited from this techniques are image recognition [38], audio [35] [39], and mixed modalities such as the work by Andrew Ng *et al* where the authors demonstrated that improved features for one single modality (e.g., video) can be learned if complementary modalities (e.g., audio and video) are present at learning time [40]. Deep learning has been applied both as supervised learning in tasks such as classification or regression, or in unsupervised scenarios such as clustering (see section 2.6). The potential for transfer learning in audio has been show, for instance, by Pons *et al* in works such as [41], where pre-trained deep learned embeddings fostered the learning performance over a dataset with a relatively small amount of annotated training examples. Finally, it is worth mentioning the recent end-to-end learning approach for audio, where neural networks have been trained directly from raw audio signals, without any prior knowledge or preliminary feature extraction[33] [42].

As an notorious example of deep learned features (also called *embeddings*), Soundnet embeddings were published in 2016 and yielded a 10% performance increase

over several environmental recognition tasks [43]. Soundnet approach proposed a student-teacher training procedure, over 2 million unlabeled online videos. The videos were automatically labeled by well established image recognition algorithms, and the obtained labels were used to teach the sound network (see Figure 10 for a general schema). This approach suggests that some high-level semantics automatically emerge in the sound network, even though it is trained without ground truth labels. Soundnet has been recently outperformed by other deep learned embeddings such as OpenL3 by Cramer, Salamon *et al* (see Figure 11) or AudioSet embeddings [44] [45].

Figure 10: SoundNet high-level architecture [43]

Figure 11: L3-Net high-level architecture [44]

2.2.2 AudioSet: Ontology, Dataset, Embeddings, FSD

AudioSet (<https://research.google.com/audioset>) [16] was published in 2017 by the Sound Understanding group in the Machine Perception Research organization at Google. It is an expanding ontology of about 600 audio event classes, and an accompanying dataset organised within the same principle. AudioSet ontology is defined as a hierarchy graph of event categories (see Figure 12 for an overall view). It covers a wide range of human and animal sounds, musical instruments and genres, and common everyday environmental sounds. This ontology is presented as an organised *vocabulary* of sound events, and can be therefore used as a in audio event detection tasks as an evaluation task [16].

Figure 12: First 2 layers of the AudioSet ontology [16]

AudioSet also provides a large dataset made up from more than 2 million human-labeled 10-second sound clips drawn from YouTube videos. This collection of clips was verified by humans, and manually annotated according to the provided ontology.

Together with the AudioSet dataset and ontology, *AudioSet embeddings* model was also published. This embeddings are a 128-dimensional audio features extracted at 1Hz (one second frame size). The audio features were extracted using a VGG-inspired acoustic model described in Hershey *et al* [45]. The model used to generate the features is available as a TensorFlow model in their GitHub repository (<https://github.com/tensorflow/models/tree/master/research/audioset>) [46].

In the upcoming methodology (chapter 3), it will be exposed that AudioSet embeddings were computed over selected datasets in order to perform experiments with the use of semantic, high-level features.

2.3 Dimensionality, time and the codebook approach

This section will introduce the curse of dimensionality, the temporality problem, statistical aggregation (its benefits and potential flaws) and how the codebook approach might be an alternative resource, specially when dealing with multiple event audio tracks.

2.3.1 The curse of dimensionality

It is not uncommon to end up with a high number of numerical descriptors when dealing with feature extraction. As an example, the Freesound feature extractor from Essentia [24] offers several dozens of extractors, each of them potentially compounded by several numerical descriptors. Since audio tracks are segmented into small frames for computation, the number of distinct features needed to describe an audio clip can considerably grow. As an example, MFCCs features have 13 dimensions, while AudioSet embeddings have 128 (multiplied by the number of obtained frames and their corresponding hop-size if applicable). Even more, sometimes multiple features are extracted simultaneously, specially in the low-level.

As dimensionality increases, the volume of space increases exponentially, so the available data becomes sparse. Within this sparsity, all data points might seem dissimilar over many dimensions. In order to obtain a statistically significant result, increasing amounts of data are needed to fill up this higher dimensional feature space. In order to maintain the model precision, the approximate amount of required data increases exponentially as dimensionality grows. Obviously, this would also mean that computational resources will increase accordingly. [47].

There is no fixed rule to overcome this issue, as the ideal number of features/dimensions will depend on the size and the quality of the training data, the algorithm of choice and the particular problem to solve. One option would be to apply domain knowledge to discern which features are more representative for a given problem, but this can be challenging because the features themselves might not be intuitive, and the problem might not be easily defined. However, automatic dimensionality reduction methods such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) allow to reduce dimensionality of the feature space. In a nutshell, PCA linearly transforms the normalized feature space by prioritizing the components that maximize the variance, while more correlated components tend to be diminished (a detailed explanation of the algorithm can be found in [48]). Although there is a wide variety of techniques to deal with dimensionality reduction, they were not used in this thesis and are out of the scope for this State of the Art. The interested reader might refer to Verleysen *et al* in [49].

2.3.2 Statistical aggregation - Pooling

Defining and computing similarity, discovering patterns, or classifying numerical time-series (like sound and music) can be challenging due to the difficulty of dealing with events that happen in time (we will refer to this issue as the "temporality problem"). For instance, in the case of comparing, the acoustic events from audio clips are almost never aligned, and perceptually similar patterns might have different lengths. Since sound is sequential, frame-base feature extraction will result in a series of feature vectors. Therefore, series of different sizes will be extracted from audio

clips of different lengths. However, in order to numerically compare two data points, fixed size vectors are usually required.

In order to obtain a fixed sized vector, it is a common practice to perform some sort of statistical aggregation over the series of feature vectors, in order to obtain a fixed-sized numerical vector that represents the original audio clip. Comparing fixed-sized vectors can be done by the use of a distance metric (e.g. euclidean distance or cosine similarity), and in a relatively reduced computing time. This statistical aggregation is also known as *pooling*. Some statistical operations that are typically performed are the mean, median, variance, standard deviation, variance of the derivative, and many more (Essentia library provides a comprehensive list of its available statistical operations in https://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/reference/std_PoolAggregator.html [24]).

Statistical aggregation is relatively appropriate when the audio contains a single sonic event. However, when there is more than a single sonic event in a track (or even a complex single sonic event) the resulting statistical features may not correspond to the different acoustic events. Figure 13 depicts a simplified example where a drum track is not well represented by the mean of its components, as it falls in a different area of the feature space. This flaw is central to the research question of this thesis, as the proposed codebook approach is an alternative to the statistical aggregation step. As we shall see in the upcoming sections, the codebook approach has proved useful in other disciplines for retaining diverse representative patterns [50].

2.3.3 Alternative temporality-aware techniques

Before dwelling upon vector quantization and bag-of-words approaches, it is worth mentioning diverse solutions to the temporality problem that could be used instead of statistical aggregation. Hidden Markov Models (HMM)[51], Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM)[52], Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)[53] or Dynamic time warping (DTW)[54] have been proved useful as classification, comparing, regression or generative solutions in time-related contexts. However, due to time limitations they

Figure 13: Representation of frame-based features from a drum kit recording, where the computed mean misleadingly falls into the hi-hat area. The same process works correctly for a single-note recording on a saxophone. The image is taken from the first two principal components after performing PCA over the features. Statistical aggregation such as the mean provides a good summarization on single sounds, but might misrepresent complex or multi-event sounds.

were not tested throughout this thesis. In the next section, the alternative vector quantization will be explained.

2.3.4 Vector Quantization - Codebook approach

Vector Quantization (VQ) is classical signal processing technique that was originally developed for lossy data compression [55]. It is the process of discretising the continuous feature space into definite regions, and quantizing the feature vectors accordingly. In other words, the feature space is partitioned, and all data points belonging to the same region are quantized to the same value. Regions are stored in a look-up table called the "codebook" or "dictionary".

Vector quantization has been widely used in applications such as speech coding [56], video encoding [57], signal compression [58], face detection [59], image encoding [60], texture synthesis [61], etc. The codebook approach can be effective, relatively understandable and easy to implement, highly parallelizable and scalable [62] [63].

There are three major procedures in vector quantization, namely codebook generation, encoding procedure and decoding procedure [64]. Figure 14 provides a

high-level diagram on a typical architecture for vector quantization. This steps will be explained in detail in the next subsections.

Figure 14: High level diagram on the codebook approach for data transmission. In this particular case: encoding input vector by nearest neighbour rule and decoding by looking at the pre-trained codebook lookup table

As we shall see, another interesting derivation of this approach is that the encoded vectors can be treated as "word" vectors, thus allowing the use of many techniques typically associated with Natural Language Processing (NLP), such as the 'Bag of Words' or 'Bag of Features' approach (see section 2.4.1 for extended explanation).

Codebook generation

The term codebook is generally used in the domain of vector quantization. The feature space is partitioned into several regions. In Figure 15 an example of partitioned two-dimensional feature space is depicted (although in reality the feature space will present many more dimensions). Each data instance can be represented by the center of its region: this step is called *codebook encoding*. It can achieve data compression, as only one point in each region needs to be stored, while the surrounding points only keep a reference to its centroid. This reference is called *codeword*, and the dictionary holding all codewords is called *codebook*. The codebook holds codewords that are supposed to roughly represent the variety of prominent patterns in the signal. We can understand the codebook as a lookup table for encoding and decoding.

In order to encode audio clips with a given codebook, the codebook needs to be pre-computed in advance. There are several techniques to generate a codebook, and

Figure 15: Vector Quantization (using k-means) over a 2-dimensional space. Each big dot corresponds to the centroid of the quantized region. In this case, the codebook would have a size of 16 codewords; each data instance would be quantized to its nearest centroid (wikimedia).

in the past years many improved algorithms for VQ codebook generation have been documented. As exposed in the codebook generation survey by Lu [50], the codebook generation might range from partitioning the feature space manually to using neural network based techniques. In this thesis, we are interested in an automatic method, yet simple to understand and with successful results in the literature [65], so the k-means clustering algorithm has been chosen (see section 2.6.1 for details on k-means). In short, k-means is a technique that creates a previously defined number of data

groups (*clusters*) from a given set of data points. In the codebook generation case, the centers (*centroid*) of each cluster will correspond to the codewords that will be stored in the codebook. This allows to partition the feature space in an unsupervised manner, by just feeding all available samples to the k-means algorithm. One main advantage of k-means algorithm is that it is fast, popular and easily implemented at large scale [66]. The example provided in Figure 15 actually depicts a VQ result, using k-means (the big blue dots are the centroids of each partition). In this Figure, each region would correspond to a codeword, so this particular example showcases a codebook of 16 words.

Codebook encoding and decoding

After the creation of the codebook, we can easily quantize any feature vector to the obtained regions. As depicted in Figure 14, each frame of the input vector will be associated to the index of its nearest codeword. This is the data compression factor: each encoded vector is now a list of indices of the codebook.

As an illustrative example, in the case of data transmission only the encoded vector (a list of indices) is sent instead of the original values. The receiver can recover the quantized vector values by looking up at the codebook indices (the codebook must be shared between the encoder and the decoder). Consequently, a good codebook must minimize the distortion between the original and the reconstructed signal [64]. Figures 16 and 17 depict similar diagrams for codebook encoding within speech and image.

Specifically, this thesis interest is centered in the encoding phase. In the resulting encoded vector, each entry encodes the presence/absence/prominence of a specific pattern in a given frame. Each codeword can be considered analog to a word, and consequently the encoded vector can be treated as a sequence of words. As we shall see in upcoming sections, Natural Language Processing techniques can be used in order to process this sequences.

Figure 16: Processing pipeline architecture for creating codebook in Vector Quantization. This particular case refers to speech processing, but any type of signal could be used.

2.4 Word embeddings

The research area of Natural Language Processing (NLP) combines knowledge from linguistics, computer science, information engineering, and artificial intelligence to process and analyze large amounts of natural language data. Reviewing this extensive field is out of the scope of this section, but the interested reader can find

Figure 17: Codebook encoding and decoding of an input vector

further resources in books such as [67] by Bird *et al.* In essence, NLP frequently involve automatic methods for speech recognition, natural language understanding, and natural language generation.

As mentioned in preceding sections, numerical representations are needed in order to train most of machine learning methods (i.e in tasks such as classification, regression, similarity, deep learning, clustering, and so on). Word embeddings are those NLP techniques where words (or phrases, or documents) are converted into numerical vectors. The optimal word embedding outcome would yield a geometric representation for words that would capture their meanings, semantic relationships and the different types of contexts they are used in. However, this is still an ongoing research. Some of this algorithms need a large amount of data and can be computationally expensive [10], while others might are computationally lighter, more understandable and practical, such as Bag-of-Words or TF-IDF which will be reviewed within this section.

Since NLP and Word Embeddings are very broad topics [68], this section will focus solely on providing the specific background to understand the upcoming Methodology and Results chapters (see chapters 3 and 4). In this context, the Bag-of-Words model will be explained (and its derived Bag-of-Features model), as it constitutes

one of the simplest and more understandable examples on how to convert a sequence of words into a fixed-sized numerical vector. Later on, TF-IDF will be looked over, as it was used in our processing pipeline explained in chapter 3. Finally, a hint on more advanced, deep learned embeddings will be provided as it is an inspirational research line for the future. The interested reader might find extended resources in the 2019 survey from Kowsari *et al* [69].

2.4.1 From Bag-of-words to Bag-of-Acoustic-Words

Bag-of-Words

The Bag-of-Words (BoW) approach was initially developed for text analysis, specially on the web. It represents a document as a Bag of Words (histogram of words), regardless of order. Words are the basic unit to count, and the only concern is how many times a word appears in documents. It is an easy way to assess the similarity between documents, by looking at the intersection of the word histograms of the compared documents. It is also an *orderless* representation, as we only count the appearance of words from a dictionary into a document, resulting in an histogram-like vector. The BoW representation is a simplistic, yet effective way of capturing the general topic/s and context of a given text [70]. The resulting vectors can then be used to perform tasks such as training a classifier (by computing similarity matrices) [71], or run text retrieval tasks such as search engines [72].

Bag-of-features

In an equivalent process to Bag Of Words for written documents, the Bag-of-Features approach will use encoded features as analog to words. The advantage of this technique is that it results in a fixed sized vector (histogram) representing a whole image or audio. In the next sections, further explanation will be provided on how this concept applies to multimedia applications, specifically to image and sound.

As already explained in section 2.3, under normal circumstances it is only possible to compare two vector with the same size. The Bag-of-Features approach allows to

transform variable size input vectors into manageable fixed-sized vector, which represents the whole original signal (despite of the loss of order). Therefore, one of the big challenges would be to create a proper dictionary (a *codebook*) of representative "codewords" (in textual language, we already now which are the possible words to be used in a language, as they are collected in a dictionary). After, we can represent any media file as an histogram of this generated words.

Bag-of-visual words

Before focusing on audio, it is worth mentioning the Bag-of-Features for image processing, as it provides a clearer intuition about how this method works. An illustrative guideline of the process is depicted in Figure 18.

To represent an image using the BoW model, an image must be treated as a document. Therefore, the bag-of-features techniques will consist on first extracting the selected features over the training patches of images, then generate a vocabulary, and finally encoding the input vector relative to their nearest "visual word". As already explained, this is know as the codebook approach (see section 2.3.4). Figure 19 depicts the referred codebook generation. Within this context, the obtained codebook will constitute a lexicon of the available visual words. This visual words are essentially a multidimensional feature vector, that represents a distinct region of the feature space.

Another illustrative example, within texture recognition, the codebook could be a global dictionary of *textons* [73]. See Figure 20 for a representation of this concept.

It is important to reiterate that one of the notorious disadvantages of the Bag-of-Features model is that it ignores the spatial relationships among the patches, which are very important in image representation. [73]. Several publications have proposed solutions to this problem, such using Gaussian Mixture Model to model the feature space and the spatial distribution of images (Chen *et al* in [74]). The inherent loss of sequentiality is a situation that will be found also when dealing with audio.

Figure 18: In this illustrative example, whole images are segmented into smaller patches which constitute the visual words. Normally, an intermediate step of feature extraction within the image patches should be performed (but it is skipped in this diagram for the sake of clarity). Finally, a fixed-size histogram is obtained by counting the frequency of each visual word. Image from <https://gurus.pyimagesearch.com/the-bag-of-visual-words-model>

Bag-of-acoustic-words

Following the Bag-of-Feature model, vector quantization of the acoustic space can be performed, and a codebook of "acoustic words" can be obtained (for example, by applying k-means clustering as previously explained in section 2.3.4). Consequently, each frame of an audio recording can be encoded as an acoustic word, and subsequently represented as a histogram over the codebook units [75]. This will be the

Figure 19: Codebook generation by way of clustering. In this archetypal case, k -dimensional numerical descriptors are extracted from a bag of small image patches. The resulting feature vectors are clustered, and the obtained centroids conform the codebook. Snapshot from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iGZpJZhqEME&t=560s>

encoding approach that will be tested in the upcoming Methodology and Results chapters (see chapter 3).

As previously stated, these encoded vectors can be treated with Natural Language Processing, analogously to sentences of words.

For instance, it has been proven that the removal of acoustic stop-words (in the language domain, these would be the high frequency non-content words like "the", "of", and so on) can benefit the algorithm performance. In [76], the acoustic stop-words are selected based on data-driven frequency-related measurements such as TF-IDF (see next section for detailed explanation on TF-IDF). This is based on the reasonable assumption that not all segments of a generic audio signal contribute equally toward defining a specific category [77].

Figure 20: The bag-of-visual-words model when encoding textures with a *texton* codebook. The resulting histograms provide a representative overview of the building blocks of each original texture.

2.4.2 TF-IDF

The TF-IDF (term frequency - inverse document frequency), is a weight that ranks the importance of a term in its contextual document corpus. It is the results of the multiplication of two metrics. TF (term frequency) is the output of the Bag-of-Words. As previously explained, TF method is based on counting the number of words in a given document, and outputting an histogram-like vector. IDF (inverse document frequency) is a normalization designed to lessen the effect of common words in the corpus. It will assign a higher weight to to words that are increasingly scarce within the document corpus.

In other words, the most frequent words in a given document will be higher ranked as representative of this document, but if these words are very common across other documents in the dataset, they will be ranked down. The underlying assumption is that relatively uncommon words that appear frequently in a document are rep-

representative of the overall topic of that document. Although this approach might seem naive, it has performed very well for a wide number of applications [69][78]. This normalization will be implemented in this thesis experiments, attempting to identify representative codewords for a given audio file, as already implemented for image processing in Yang *et al* and in SMC by Kim *et al* [79] [76].

TF-IDF provides a lightweight, well understood model to compute fixed-sized embeddings from a text corpus (in our particular case, a corpus of codeword sequences). Under this criteria, it has been selected as embedding method to assess similarity between audio clips. However, even though TF-IDF or BoW representations provide weights to different words, they are not able to capture the word meaning, and every single word is considered a different token, ignoring synonymity, grammar, order and context.

As the linguist J. R. Firth said in 1935, "The complete meaning of a word is always contextual, and no study of meaning apart from context can be taken seriously." Even if due to time limitations they were not used in this thesis experiments, the emerging field of neural network embeddings provide a promising solution to the problem of word contextualization.

2.4.3 Neural Network Embeddings: Word2Vec

One profitable use of neural networks and deep learning is embedding, which is a technique to encode discrete variables (such as words) as continuous vectors. Neural network embeddings have been successful because they can meaningfully represent categories in the transformed space. When dealing with large input vectors (eg large sparse vectors representing words), an embedding will ideally place semantically similar inputs close together in the embedded space, thus capturing some of the semantics of the input vector. Nowadays, word embeddings are one of the most popular use cases, and probably the most notorious example is the Word2Vec model [68].

Word2Vec can be trained on a huge text corpus (for example, on a dump of the

English wikipedia) which allow to embed words in a multidimensional space. Although the implementation details fall out of the scope for this thesis, the seminal technique is a combination of relating the nearest words between them (continuous bag-of-words) and a prediction step (skip-gram), which will be optimised along the learning process. The curious reader will find a thorough explanation of the inner workings of the Word2Vec model in the seminal Mikolov *et al* paper [80] and Goldberg commentary [81].

Neural networks word embeddings are able to encode similarity and semantic relationships between words of the text corpus. For example, Word2Vec considers "big" and "bigger" as close to each other in the vector space. An illustrative example of GloVe [82], another neural network embedding, is provided in Figure 21.

2.5 A note on unsupervised learning

Unsupervised learning is a broad range of machine learning and data mining techniques that are capable of finding patterns in unlabeled data [84]. The already explained NLP algorithms and PCA dimensionality reduction can be considered as unsupervised learning examples. One paramount branch of unsupervised learning is clustering, which will be explained in the next section.

In the context of this work, it is essential that the proposed methodology is based on unsupervised techniques. To be able to process and extract meaning from large audio collections such as the Freesound database, it is not feasible to ultimately rely on human supervision. In spite of the work already invested in tasks such as labeling metadata for audios or categorizing a collection of sound clips to create a dataset, the amount of data is so big that automatic methods to extract patterns from the data itself are necessary.

2.6 Clustering

In the preceding sections of this State of the Art chapter, several concepts have been introduced in order to provide sufficient background to understand the experiments

Figure 21: A 2D projection of the 300-dimensional vector space of GloVe. The lines depict numerical relationships between related words. In this example, pairs of words differentiated by gender are mapped in a similar distance. Other similar algebraic relationships have been found for countries to capital cities, companies and their CEOs, and forms of the same word. [83].

carried out in the next chapters of this thesis. Clustering constitutes the final step on our processing pipeline (see chapter 3.1). This section will provide a general overview about clustering, a more detailed explanation on the k-means algorithm and the review of some relevant performance metrics.

Clustering is a process of organizing objects into groups whose members are similar in some way. It is an unsupervised learning method that enables data analysis and exploration, and discovery of interesting patterns in the data. The central problem is to arrange a given collection of unlabeled data into meaningful groups (called *clusters*). These clusters should be identified in such a way that objects in the same cluster are more similar between each other than to the objects of the other clusters

[2]. The definition of similarity might differ across applications, but the fundamental idea persists in placing related elements in the same group. Before being able to run any clustering algorithm on a dataset, the data points have to be represented as mutually comparable vectors. To achieve this task, embedding techniques (see section 2.4), statistical pooling (see section 2.3.2) or any alternative method (see section 2.3.3) can be applied to obtain fixed-size, comparable vectors.

It is important to point out that within clustering techniques, there is no absolute guarantee of recovering a ground truth. For instance, choosing the correct number of clusters is a hard task. On the other hand, the algorithms might fall into local minima and be sensitive to initialization, although there are several techniques to minimize this issue.

In the next section, k-means will be looked at in detail. k-means will be used in our implementation for codebook generation. It was selected because it is relatively fast and simple to understand, and backed up by other literature on codebook generation [66][74][77][79]. In data mining literature, there is abundance of alternatives to perform clustering. To review them is out of the scope for this chapter, but some relevant algorithms are Hierarchical Clustering, K-medoids, Fuzzy clustering, Spectral Clustering or DBSCAN [2]. Figure 22 presents a table with different types of clustering methods.

2.6.1 k-means clustering

The k-means clustering technique has been widely used since it was published in the 60s [85]. It is easy to implement and computationally economical. It requires the number of resulting clusters to be defined in advance (which can be far from easy in some scenarios). Within the table presented in Figure 22, k-means would be considered a partitioning method.

The classical algorithm will iteratively assign each data point as belonging to the cluster of its nearest mean (called *centroids*), recompute the mean to obtain the new centroids, and repeat the process until convergence is reached [86]. An illustration

Method	General Characteristics
Partitioning methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Find mutually exclusive clusters of spherical shape – Distance-based – May use mean or medoid (etc.) to represent cluster center – Effective for small- to medium-size data sets
Hierarchical methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Clustering is a hierarchical decomposition (i.e., multiple levels) – Cannot correct erroneous merges or splits – May incorporate other techniques like microclustering or consider object “linkages”
Density-based methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Can find arbitrarily shaped clusters – Clusters are dense regions of objects in space that are separated by low-density regions – Cluster density: Each point must have a minimum number of points within its “neighborhood” – May filter out outliers
Grid-based methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Use a multiresolution grid data structure – Fast processing time (typically independent of the number of data objects, yet dependent on grid size)

Figure 22: Overview of different types of clustering methods. Some specific algorithms might combine more than a single method [2].

of this iterative process is provided in Figure 23. Many variations and heuristic enhancements have been developed over the years for diverse applications [87], and are offered by software libraries like scikit-learn (<https://scikit-learn.org/>) [88].

Figure 23: Clustering using the k-means method; the centroid(mean) of each cluster is marked by a + [2].

k-means is a common solution for segmenting multi-dimensional data. As such, it can be understood as a vector quantization technique, for instance when generating

a codebook as seen in section 2.3.4. In this process, each resulting cluster centroid will become a codeword. Since the number of clusters needs to be defined in advance when running k-means, the size of the resulting codebook can be manually chosen and deliberately planned.

clustering evaluation metrics

Evaluation of clustering results is a difficult task, and it is not a solved problem yet [89]. Different clusterings can reveal different interesting patterns in data. Thus, evaluating by comparing to a known ground truth might not be sufficient to assess the performance of a clustering method [90].

However, several clustering evaluation metrics aim to assess the quality of the results generated by a clustering method [2]. There are two main approaches which depend on the availability of a ground truth. Here, *ground truth* is the ideal clustering that is often built by human experts, usually by applying labels to each input data point. When this ground truth is accessible, extrinsic metrics can be used. Otherwise, intrinsic evaluation metrics can be adopted when a ground truth is not available. Within this thesis, we are interested in *extrinsic methods*, because our datasets of choice will be labeled (in FSD, the AudioSet ontology labels can be considered as a ground truth).

Nevertheless, human subjective (*manual*) evaluation should not be dismissed [91] and will be performed along these automatic metrics. As concisely exposed by Farber *et al* regarding extrinsic methods: "from a knowledge discovery point of view, the reproduction of known knowledge may not necessarily be the intended result" [89]. Subjective exploration and qualitative analysis of the obtained clusters might lead to the discovery of interesting patterns that were not labeled as the ground truth [92]. With this in mind, the selected methods will serve as a numerical guideline, that can serve, at least, to identify bad clustering.

Intrinsic metrics are a set of techniques that evaluate the correctness based on how the clusters are separated. These metrics can be used in the absence of a ground truth [93]. However, even if they can be used as a guideline, a high performance

according to this type of metrics does not guarantee good clustering performance [2]. This is why in our work we will make use of the ground truth available within FSD, a dataset organized in categories following the AudioSet ontology.

When using *extrinsic* evaluation metrics, assessment of the clustering can be done by comparing the obtained clusters with the original ground truth. In particular, the metrics to be used in the processing pipeline to be explained in chapter 3 will be enumerated below [89] [91]

- Purity: Each cluster is assigned to the class which is most frequent in the cluster, and an accuracy measure is obtained [93].
- Adjusted Mutual Info: A measure of how one probability distribution is different from a second [94].
- Adjusted Rand: computes a similarity measure between two clusterings by considering all pairs of samples and counting pairs that are assigned in the same or different clusters in the predicted and true clusterings [95].

The scikit-learn library provides out-of-the-box implementations for Adjusted Mutual Info and Adjusted Rand among several other alternative evaluation metrics for cluster analysis results (<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/classes.html#clustering-metrics>) [88].

2.7 Illustrative examples

In this section, each paragraph will outline an illustrative work that became referential in the development of the methodology presented in chapter 3. The variety and success of these experiments provided a solid foundation to attempt our clustering of multi-event, diverse audio collections with the codebook approach.

One of the most inspirational sources in the personal quest for a research topic was the paper for bio-acoustic bird species classification by Salamon *et al* [96]. In this experiment, MFCCs were extracted from a bird call audio dataset, and

the resulting frames were fed into a k-means algorithm to obtain the respective codebook (256 words in this case). The results were summarized using statistical aggregation, before finally training a classifier to perform the bird call classification. In this particular work, this "shallow approach" was compared to an opposed "deep learning" approach, showing similar accuracy results. Interestingly, both methods showed different tendencies in their respective confusion matrices, so the authors finally proposed a late-fusion approach between "shallow" and "deep" outcomes that pushed the overall performance to a state-of-the-art level.

A similar solution is presented by Vaizman *et al* regarding an end-to-end codebook approach for audio content representation and music information retrieval [97]. This end-to-end approach can be summarised by an encoding-pooling scheme. Low-level audio features were extracted from short audio frames and then encoded using a pre-trained codebook. Finally, the encoded song is pooled together in a single compact vector in order to perform query-by-tag or query-by-example retrieval.

In [77], the images of the dataset are previously embedded with a VGGish model. Then, a codebook approach is performed with k-means clustering. Searching for similar images becomes a process of comparing the query image against the codebook of embedded images in the high-dimensional feature space and retrieving the closest one. In summary, the paper proposes a Bag-of-Features approach, but with deep learned features. This approach is analog to the one we study in the case of audio representation using the AudioSet embeddings (which are also a VGGish model trained on spectrograms) in the upcoming chapters.

The codebook approach has been successfully implemented in examples such as the mentioned above, but *to our knowledge*, it has not been used yet in unsupervised clustering for large, multi-event audio datasets. Within this thesis, the research experiments will focus on applying a codebook approach for the clustering of sound collections. In the next chapter, the designed methodology for our experiments will be reviewed.

Chapter 3

Methodology

Within this section, the designed methodology to perform our experiments will be reviewed. The codebase and the custom dataset are both delivered in the accompanying Github project (<https://github.com/lluissuros/codebook-approach>). In addition, the datasets used to perform the experiments will also be described.

3.1 Processing pipeline

3.1.1 General overview

Complementing this section, a high-level diagram of the processing pipeline architecture is presented in Figure 24.

Given a dataset of feature vectors series, the codebook will be generated. This codebook will be used to encode the feature vectors, so each frame will be encoded as its nearest codeword in the feature space (see section 2.3.4 for extended explanation). This encoded vector can be treated analogous to a text, where each codeword is analog to a natural language word. In our particular processing pipeline, TF-IDF (see section 2.4.2) is performed in order to reward less common codewords. Since the output of TF-IDF is a fixed-sized vector, a similarity matrix can be computed. This similarity matrix is used by the clustering algorithm to finally obtain the clusters.

Figure 24: General overview of the presented processing pipeline. Note that AudioSet embeddings are displayed as the original numerical features, but any other feature extractor can be used instead.

The presented code is modular enough to allow the use of different NLP algorithms in order to produce alternative similarity matrices. For example, histogram intersection was used in a previous iteration instead of TF-IDF (see figure 25 for an example of histograms under the Bag-of-acoustic-Words model). Different clustering techniques are also easy to plug-in (as an example, k-means was previously used in an earlier iteration before switching to k-nn graph-based clustering [98][99] which proved to be much more faster and easier to render in the web browser).

An additional functionality is the web-visualization tool, which allows to interact with the obtained clusters in a web browser. The required data for this web application is also created within the processing pipeline.

3.1.2 Codebook generation

As previously explained in section 2.3.4, a bag-of-features approach was chosen for the codebook creation, where all the individual feature vectors are used as data points to perform k-means clustering, and the obtained cluster centroids are then stored as the "codewords". With this approach, each codeword can be considered the representation of the nearest frames in the feature space. The number of clusters

Figure 25: Audio clips encoded with codebook can be summarized as histograms using the Bag-of-acoustic-words model.

(which need to be defined in advance for k-means) will be equal to the size of the dictionary. As explained in the State of the Art, once the codebook is created, each feature vector can be encoded to its nearest codeword, thus obtaining a vector of codewords for each original audio clip. This vector of codewords is analog to a natural language word sentence, and can be treated as such with any NLP technique.

FSD consists in a dataset divided by multiple subdatasets according to the AudioSet ontology (the detailed composition of the FSD version will be detailed in the upcoming section 3.2.1). In order to generate the codebook, two different approaches were designed. Since no prior literature could be found regarding this distinction, these approaches have been called "global" and "local" codebook. It is still not clear which strategy performs better (clarifying this issue has been a point of interest within this thesis, and will be reviewed in the Discussion chapter), so both methods are maintained in the codebase in order to offer the flexibility of choosing either approach, or even computing both for later analysis.

Global codebook

When having multiple subdatasets within a global dataset (e.g. within FSD), one single global codebook is computed, using all feature vectors from all frames belonging to the available subdatasets. Each subdataset can be subsequently encoded against the obtained global codebook. Given the increased size of the data points used for the k-means clustering, obtaining the global codebook can be significantly more expensive computationally than the local codebook.

Local codebook

A codebook is pre-computed locally for every individual sub-dataset. Each sub-dataset is encoded against its particular codebook.

3.1.3 Cluster evaluation

In addition to the codebook-based clustering results, an additional clustering using statistical aggregation is also computed in order to compare both processing pipelines. Specifically, mean is computed over each feature as an statistical aggregator. Comparisons are performed by analysing the obtained evaluation metrics, and by subjective evaluation with the use of the web-visualization tool.

Rendering the obtained clusters for subjective evaluation

In the presented version of the processing pipeline, k-nearest-neighbours (k-nn) graph-based clustering is used [99][98]. Previously, a k-means approach was tested, but it was relatively more expensive computationally. This graph-based clustering allowed subjective exploration and analysis of the resulting clusters; for this subjective evaluation, a two-dimensional representation of the k-nn graph clustering is rendered in a web browser.

In this rendered visualization, each node corresponds to an audio clip from the clustered collection, and the edges connect the most similar nodes together. A force layout allows to visualize and explore the graph [100]. An example using force-layout

on a web browser in provided in Figure 26. In our particular implementation, when the user hovers the mouse over a given node, the corresponding Freesound audio clip is downloaded and played (through the Freesound API), allowing immediate exploratory feedback. At the same time, the associated Freesound labels for the hovered audio clip are also prompted.

Figure 26: Force layout example on a web browser, using D3.js library (<https://d3js.org>).

In retrospective, this method proved very useful when subjectively assessing the quality of the obtained clusters. In the accompanying Github project (<https://github.com/lluissuros/codebook-approach>), instructions on how to boot the web server and connect the web client (web-visualization tool) are provided. For

the sake of completeness within this thesis, screenshots of some relevant clusterings will be offered to the reader in the upcoming Results chapter.

Evaluation metrics

Clustering evaluation metrics are computed against the FSD annotated ground truth. Some typical evaluation metrics are used: purity, adjusted mutual info, and adjusted rand (see previous chapter 2.6.1 for extended details).

Custom Python helper libraries have been developed to compute these evaluation metrics among different clusterings, offering a numerical comparison. These libraries were used to compare different codebook sizes between each other, and to compare the statistical aggregation (using the mean) against the codebook approach. The helper code is provided within the delivered Github project (<https://github.com/11uissuros/codebook-approach>).

3.2 Datasets

The starting point of the codebook approach is a dataset. In this regard, two different datasets were used in the experiments. At first, the current FSD version was used to test the global and local codebook end-to-end processing pipeline. Later on, with the intention of narrowing down the experimentation scope, a custom dataset with acoustic scenes was created.

Before being used as input for the processing pipeline, audio features need to be computed from the audio tracks, as detailed in the upcoming section 3.2.3.

3.2.1 Freesound Datasets (FSD)

Freesound Dataset (FSD) [18] is a collection of manually annotated Freesound sounds, hierarchically organized following the AudioSet ontology [16]. A thorough description of FSD is provided in the State of the Art section 2.1.5.

Since the official FSD release was not yet available in at the time of writing (summer 2019), some categories were selected that were presenting enough sounds. Several

subsets of the dataset were extracted for being able to learn and apply our approach on different cases corresponding to different audio themes. This will allow to answer our research questions on the codebook approach suitability for diverse types of sound collections.

In our FSD working version, 45 sound subdatasets were available, where each belongs to an AudioSet category. Around 30k audio tracks make up the whole collection, where each subdataset might contain from few hundred elements to a maximum about 10k. FSD can be used as a ground truth for extrinsic evaluation of our experiments, where one possible goal could be to optimize the resemblance between the automatically created clusters and the original labels.

3.2.2 Creating a custom dataset: acoustic scenes

After the lessons learned in the first experiment with FSD (which are detailed in the forthcoming Results section 4.1.2), a custom dataset was curated in order to further experiment with the codebook approach. 150 field recordings from the Freesound platform were gathered, and labeled under the premise of representing either "human" or "natural" acoustic scenes. Since most of the FSD audio tracks were relatively short (less than 10 seconds), longer audios were favoured in this new dataset, thus increasing the amount of acoustic events in every single sound.

With this new custom multi-event audio dataset, the main hypothesis from this thesis was evaluated, under the belief that the combination of TF-IDF and codebook advantages (analogy with text documents, lower rank of common codewords, potential to capture small patterns in the data) could boost the accuracy on the clustering results in comparison with statistical aggregation. In addition, since AudioSet Embeddings use frame sizes of one second, the use of longer tracks would translate into longer encoded vectors, which might be of interest when processing them using NLP techniques.

In this particular case, global and local codebook are equivalent because there is only one single dataset, hence all available frames were used for feeding the codebook

generation.

3.2.3 Features

In order to use an audio dataset, numerical features must be extracted in a preliminary step in order to proceed with further computing (see State of the Art section 2.2.1). The provided code is designed to make use of any kind of feature vectors, as long as they are formatted as a *numpy* array [101]. In the context of this thesis experiments, both MFFCs and AudioSet embeddings were used.

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter will present two experiments based on the methodology defined in the preceding chapter 3. The experiment results are introduced in chronological order and expand on each other.

4.1 Experiment 1: Codebook approach over FSD

4.1.1 Experiment Setup

As explained in section 3.2, a provisional snapshot of the FSD containing 45 sub-dataset was used at the time of writing. AudioSet embeddings were computed over all tracks and saved as *numpy* arrays.

In this exploratory experiment, both a global codebook and 45 local codebooks were computed. The global codebook was computed using all frames of all the 30k tracks, while each local codebook was computed using the available frames in the respective subdataset. A similarity matrix was computed after using TF-IDF normalization, and was fed into the final clustering stage. FSD labels were used as a ground truth to compute evaluation metrics.

4.1.2 Experiment results

In general, the codebook approach didn't improve the performance on the evaluation metrics in comparison to just performing statistical aggregation (mean over features). By the analysis of the metrics, only an average of 10% of the subdatasets improved its results with the codebook approach. Even more, the particular subdatasets obtaining better results on the codebook varied depending on the codebook size and the global/local codebook strategy. The difference on the metrics was narrow in most of the cases.

Many reasons come up when trying to explain why the statistical aggregation works better within this version of FSD. Some of the most important points are presented below in bullet points, together with the proposed solutions. These solutions, together with the vagueness of the obtained results, led to the design of the second experiment.

- **Short sounds:**

The majority of audios comprised by FSD were relatively short. In an earlier snapshot of the FSD [18], the authors referenced that 78% of the clips were shorter than 30 seconds, and 40% were less than 6 seconds. This might result in too short feature vectors when using AudioSet embeddings, specially since this type of features require one second window size. After being encoded by the pre-trained codebook, most clips resulted in short codeword sentences that could be sub-optimal when dealing with NLP techniques such as TF-IDF.

Therefore, in the next experiment, a custom dataset was collected favouring longer sounds. Also MFCC's (which require a much shorter window size) were computed in the next experiment in order to experiment with longer encoded tracks.

- **Audios without multiple events:**

The FSD dataset contained a majority of single event clips for many subdatasets, according to the posterior subjective exploration with the web-visualization

tool. When dealing with this type of sounds, the statistical aggregation might become representative enough and work just fine. The codebook approach might show better results when dealing with sound recordings that contain multiple events, since the codebook helps to retain small patterns instead of performing an overall averaging.

Therefore, in order to better explore the codebook approach capabilities, sounds containing multiple events were favoured in next experiment.

- **AudioSet embeddings might be high-level enough:**

AudioSet embeddings are designed to achieve an AudioSet ontology categorization by implementing a neural network architecture trained over an annotated large audio dataset [35]. It is expected that the resulting embedded frames will be more representative of the underlying audio clips (on the contrary, lower-level features might show big differences between different frames). AudioSet embeddings have improved performance over low-level MFCCs in clustering processes, retaining semantic correspondence with the original audio clips. This could lead to the conclusion that a codebook approach might not be needed.

Even if the codebook approach proved to be unnecessary when dealing with AudioSet embeddings, it could still hold relevant with lower level features. Since extracting AudioSet embeddings is computationally much more expensive, at the present moment traditional lower level features are being used in many applications. Additionally, since the accuracy did not decrease heavily, the codebook approach could still be useful in combination with AudioSet embeddings, for example in the field of interpretability (this idea will be expanded in the next Discussion chapter).

Therefore, in the next experiment, also MFCCs were extracted on the new custom dataset, in order to explore the codebook approach over low level feature extraction techniques.

4.2 Experiment 2: Codebook approach over acoustic scenes dataset

4.2.1 Experiment Setup

Observing the relative low performance of the codebook approach over FSD, a custom dataset containing diverse acoustic scene was created (see section 3.2.2).

This custom dataset contains 150 field recordings, labeled as "natural" vs "human". In this particular case, global and local codebook are equivalent because there is only one single dataset, hence all available frames were used for feeding the codebook generation.

Both MFCCs and AudioSet embeddings were extracted from the audio clips and saved as *numpy* arrays. The same whole processing pipeline was executed over both feature types, and the different results will be explained in the upcoming sections.

A note on subjective cluster analysis

It is important to point out that the forthcoming cluster descriptions come from the single subjective analysis of the author, with occasional help of a couple of people. Retrospectively, it would have been advisable to design a less potentially biased experiment for a larger group of people. This experiment fell out of scope for this thesis due to time limitations.

Subjective exploratory analysis was a basic tool within the development process, and the author considers this information valuable and representative of the presented methodology and results. Screenshots of the web-visualization tool (see section 3.1.3) are provided as a guide to follow the cluster descriptions. Only very clear cluster characteristics were written down in these descriptions, with the intention of leaving aside weak assumptions that could have been misleading.

In the upcoming sections, MFCCs and AudioSet embedded clustering results will be reviewed separately. In the next Discussion chapter, these results will be compared

and presented holistically.

4.2.2 MFCC: Experiment Results

Computing performance

MFCCs were computed over the audio clips of the custom dataset. The obtained MFCCs feature vectors were fed into the processing pipeline. Codebook sizes of 64, 128, 256, 512, 1024 and 2048 were tested.

Computational time consumed in order to obtain the codebook is represented in Table 1. It is clear that computation grew exponentially when the number of words increased. Within the current implementation, all available feature vectors are used as data points for the codebook creation. In this particular case, since MFCCs use a small window size of 2048 samples (around 50 milliseconds), and the dataset contains many long sounds on the order of minutes, the overall count of available frames went up to 200k. This affected dramatically the codebook computation, compared to the Audioset embeddings version, which are presented in Table 2 and will be discussed in section 4.2.3. Since the number of words correspond to the cluster centroids obtained from clustering all available frames, the code could be more attentive to this computing performance issue in future iterations. In the current implementation, k-means is used to compute the codebook. Although it is outside of the scope for the present thesis, a different vector quantization technique (or simply a more performant clustering algorithm) could be introduced. Also, using all available frames as data points for the Bag-Of-Features might not be necessary. A random selection or a more sophisticated method to obtain a reasonable sized sample from all the available frames could prove to be sufficient, specially when dealing with limited computational resources such as a personal laptop.

Clustering analysis

MFCCs frames are small, and presumably the obtained codewords are much less semantic than the obtained with Audioset embeddings. This assumption corresponded with the obtained clusters, where subjective analysis showed that sounds

Table 1: Computational time taken to extract the codebook for MFCCs on the Acoustic Scenes Custom Dataset , on a Macbook 2,7 GHz Intel Core i5 with 8Gb RAM.

Number of codewords	Time performance (in minutes)
64	3.5
128	12
256	32.5
512	77.5
1024	180 (3 hours)
2048	420 (7 hours)

are basically grouped by spectral similarity and other low level traits such as silence predominance.

The resulting codebook-based clusters were fairly similar among different codebook sizes, and interestingly they had noticeable differences with the statistical aggregation clustering. Figure 27 is provided as a reference to observe evolution of clustering across increasing codebook sizes. The results obtained with statistical aggregation are also included in the figure. According to this observed similarity across number of words, and in relation with the computing performance issues shown in Table 1, in this particular case a small sized codebook should be favoured.

In order to explain the obtained clusterings, 64-word codebook results will be used below as an illustrative example. The obtained clusters were also fed into the web-visualization tool in order to examine the results subjectively. Figure 28 is provided as a reference for the obtained clusters. While all clusters show a diversity regarding the origin of their recordings (there was not an obvious *nature versus civilization* discrimination), there are some common traits - observed under subjective analysis- that will be detailed below:

- Cluster A: This cluster contained clips of high activity, with very little silence and spectrally rich both in the frequential low-end and -specially- in the high-end. Some of the sounds came from markets, busy urban environments and

high-energy natural environments (ocean, jungle, rainstorm).

- Cluster B: This cluster interestingly retained almost all sounds belonging to high-energy crowd activities such as clapping, booing, cheering or applauding. It would be possible to think that the codebook could abstract some of this elements. However, a very similar cluster was formed under the statistical aggregation processing pipeline, which could mean that these sounds were statistically very close in the feature space. It is worth mentioning that the statistical aggregation cluster included other sounds that were not related to the mentioned activities in Cluster B, as it seems only the high-energy recordings prevailed in this one.
- Cluster C: This cluster contained sounds from diverse origins and with similar traits as the ones in Cluster A, but without so much frequential high and low end, probably due to inferior technical specifications in the recording itself (in other words, probably less capable microphones or recording devices were used, or maybe the recordings were filtered afterwards).
- Cluster D: This cluster contained very low-energy recordings such as room tones, quiet office ambiences, and quiet field recordings (for instance, a sunrise in the nature). A couple of the recordings contained a strong, short sound but surrounded by a quiet overall ambience (for example a thunder followed by a quiet rumble). The algorithm seems to favour the overall quietness in these cases and not to specially reward the louder event.
- Cluster E: This cluster interestingly discriminated a majority low-energy recordings, such as office ambiences, nature recordings and some Foley recordings, which particularly contained soft or silent background ambiences, with scattered sonic events happening, such as chairs moving, mouse clicks, machines, loud birds, or Foley actions. When inspecting the statistical aggregation clustering, these sounds tend to be distributed across the lowest energy clusters, but not particularly grouped together like in the codebook case. It is therefore a convincing possibility that the algorithm could recognize this property of

quiet background with distinct louder events, probably as a peculiar distribution in the encoded histogram.

- Cluster F: This cluster presented similar traits as Cluster E, but it contained recordings that had a noisier background and with increased presence of the foreground louder events. It contained sounds such as strong footsteps, water drops, office sounds with office wheelchairs, markets, faucets dropping or light rain recordings.
- Cluster G: After subjective evaluation, this cluster didn't present enough characteristic traits to be described.

A common property of the obtained clusterings (regardless the codebook size) is that high-energy, event-dense recordings (depicted in Figure 28 as A, B and C) were clearly discriminated from low-energy recordings (depicted in Figure 28 as D and E). Therefore, in Figure 27, this energy poles have been indicated on each graph. The clusterings presented some peculiarities across different codebook sizes, specially regarding the overall number of individual clusters (a minimum of 6 and a maximum of 8 for this particular case), but the relative ordering between the nodes in the graph was solidly maintained. This discrimination over event density is particularly interesting and could be used to identify foreground events against their particular background. In this regard, (subjectively) comparing the results with the statistical aggregation clustering, seems that the codebook approach performs significantly better in grouping together sounds that have both similar foreground and similar background perceptual attributes (the same sounds were more dispersed on the mean clustering, even though the high versus low energy sounds was retained in both approaches). Although this is far from being a strong claim, it is consistent with the central hypothesis: the codebook approach might help to preserve some of the original patterns when dealing with diverse, multi-event sounds.

4.2.3 Audioset Embeddings: Experiment Results

Computing performance

Audioset embeddings were extracted over the custom acoustic scene dataset and saved into *numpy* arrays. The resulting feature vectors were fed into the processing pipeline, for codebook sizes (number of words) of 64, 128, 256, 512. Not enough data was available to compute meaningful clusters for 1024 and 2048 size. Computational time consumed in order to compute the codebook is represented in Table 2.

In this case, we can see that codebook computation (again, using the same k-means algorithm) did not grow exponentially (unlike the MFCCs case shown in Table 1) but linearly. Since AudioSet embeddings are designed to be high-level and require a window size of about one second, there were fewer frames to feed the codebook generation step. Around 5000 overall frames were provided to create the codebook. These frames were now 128-dimension (for 13-dimension on MFCCs), but the k-means algorithm offered a more suitable performance. As stated in section 4.2.2, in a further iteration of the code the performance regarding the codebook computation should be handled with attention. Particularly in the MFCCs case, the computing time could become unacceptable, specially when computing local codebooks, whereas the Audioset experiment showed a more promising number.

Within the codebook generation, there is a check on the code to avoid creating the codebook if there is not at least 10 data points per centroid. This minimum was set heuristically. Accordingly, both 1024 and 2048 size codebooks couldn't be computed for this dataset due to not having enough data points to create meaningful clusters.

Clustering analysis

The resulting clusters were fairly similar under subjective analysis, specially from 256-word codebook upwards, so 256-word codebook results will be used below as a representative example for the resulting clustering. The obtained clusters were also fed into the web-visualization tool in order to explore and examine the results subjectively. Figure 29 is provided as a reference for the upcoming descriptions. In

Table 2: Computational time taken to extract the codebook for AudioSet Embeddings on the Acoustic Scenes dataset, on a Macbook 2,7 GHz Intel Core i5 with 8Gb RAM.

Number of codewords	Time performance (in seconds)
64	3.5
128	7
256	10
512	20
1024	not enough data to compute
2048	not enough data to compute

this case, AudioSet ontology classes [16] are used in order to categorize and describe each cluster.

- Cluster A: This cluster contained mainly recordings of people talking, in busy environments (such as markets, streets, crowds) with a lot of simultaneous events happening. This cluster was consistent and semantic.

These are the AudioSet categories that matched this cluster after subjective evaluation:

- Human sounds > Human Voice > Speech > "Male Speech", "Female speech", "Conversation"
 - Human sounds > Human group actions > "Clapping", "Cheering", "Applause", "Chatter", "Crowd"
 - Sounds of things > Vehicle > "Motor vehicle"
 - Channel, environment and background > "Outside, urban or manmade", "Inside, public space"
- Cluster B: The most common quality of the sounds within this cluster was that all sounds were *indoor*. Recordings had less overall activity than the ones in cluster A. This cluster contained sounds from people talking (inside halls), acoustic scenes of church, big halls, elevators.

These are the AudioSet categories that matched this cluster after subjective evaluation:

- Channel, environment and background > "Reverberation", "Inside, public space", "Inside, large room or hall", "Inside, small room"
- Human sounds > Human Voice > Speech > "Male Speech", "Female speech", "Conversation"
- Human sounds > Human locomotion > "Walk, footsteps"
- Cluster C: This was the least coherent cluster under subjective analysis. It contained a variety of sounds, for example printer, helicopter, office ambience, water flush, birds, thunderstorm, water stream or cattle.
- Cluster D: The most common quality of the sounds within this cluster was that all sounds were *outdoor*, mainly recordings of nature. This cluster included recordings of birds, horses, fire camp, forest, jungle, and ocean waves.

These are the AudioSet categories that matched this cluster after subjective evaluation:

- Channel, environment and background > "Outside, rural or natural"
- Animal > Wild animals > Bird > "Bird vocalization, bird call, bird song"
- Animal > Wild animals > Insect > "Cricket"
- Natural sounds > Fire > "Crackle"
- Natural sounds > Water > "Ocean"
- Natural sounds > Wind > "Rustling leaves"
- Cluster E: The most common quality of the sounds within this cluster was that sounds were related with *water*, or had relatively big chunks of *silence*. This cluster included sounds of water bottle, underwater recordings, steps on water, faucet, flush, gurgling, pouring, ice glass, cowbell, coins, dinnerware, wind, clapping and computer mouse clicks.

These are the AudioSet categories that matched this cluster after subjective evaluation:

- Source-ambiguous sounds > "Silence"
- Natural sounds > Water > "Gurgling", "Stream"
- Sounds of things > Bell > "Cowbell"
- Sounds of things > Domestic sounds, home sounds > "Cutlery, silverware"
- Natural sounds > Wind > "Wind noise (microphone)"

After this results, it becomes apparent that AudioSet embeddings are offering a more semantic clustering. In order to test what is the effect of the codebook approach in contrast with statistical aggregation, both clusterings were compared with the web-visualization tool. Despite some structural differences (mean-based clustering had 8 clusters in this case), both results were fairly similar and the statistical aggregation approach was also able to capture the similarities between sounds exposed in the preceding list. It is possible to conclude that for this dataset, codebook approach didn't add a significant layer of improvement, despite the extra processing. Probably AudioSet embeddings are high-level enough, as was also pointed out in section 4.1.2.

In the next Discussion chapter, the results presented in this section will be analysed and some conclusions will be provided.

Figure 27: Snapshots of all obtained clusterings for different codebook size. The obtained clusterings were fairly similar, although in the visualization some might be reversed. The plus (+) and minus (-) signs are provided for orientation (plus indicates the areas containing sound with high activity, and minus the opposite)

Figure 28: MFCCs clustering with 64-word codebook

Figure 29: Audioset Embedding clustering with 256-word codebook

Chapter 5

Discussion and Future Work

In this thesis, we were interested in performing experiments that could elucidate if the codebook approach could provide interesting benefits when clustering multi-event audio collections. In this final chapter, the results obtained are analysed and expanded in a bullet point style. Ideas for future work are also mentioned alongside.

- **Datasets:** The available snapshot of Freesound Dataset provided a valid ground truth, but the evaluation metrics were not explanatory enough to reach for clear conclusions. Nevertheless, these metrics became a very valuable resource, as they allowed to experiment with many different sound categories datasets (the current version contained 45 different subsets belonging to diverse AudioSet categories, labeled by humans).

In the particular case of this thesis, another dataset was created to focus on multi-event, longer acoustic scenes. It was a prior assumption in the research question that the codebook could potentially retain some patterns of the underlying acoustic events. Subjective exploration hints towards a slightly positive impression, but far away from being a conclusive response to the original hypothesis. Retrospectively, acoustic scenes are hard to cluster even for humans, as they may be interpreted in many different ways. Regarding the clustering results with AudioSet embeddings, AudioSet ontology was a helpful resource

to identify certain sound categories, thus enabling a kind of "objective" evaluation on the clusters (however, the clustering itself proved very similar to the obtained with statistical aggregation). In relation to lower-level MFCC, although the clusters denoted certain commonalities in regards to energy, timbre and silence preeminence, categorizing and describing the clusters in a clear manner was more problematic.

In order to research in more detail if the codebook is indeed retaining certain patterns of interest, maybe a synthetic dataset could be created with recognizable sonic events artificially spread in multiple audio clips. This way the evaluation could be much more clearer and controlled (but at the same time, the underlying audio clips would be unrealistic, and not representative of real sounds like many of the Freesound content). Another option would be to try the same processing pipeline under a variety of datasets where multi-event audios abound. As an example, musical loops or percussion loops have the potential to be good candidates on using a codebook approach.

- **Interpretability:**

An interesting research line that was not properly attempted is interpretability. In future developments, an histogram-like output from the encoded vectors could provide a way to understand the building blocks of a given audio clip. Figure 30 provides an illustrative example and explanation of the exposed concept. With a creative approach to the presentation of those codewords (for example, by providing a sonification approach where those codewords are converted into longer sounds by way of granular/concatenative synthesis), the interested researcher/user could hear, explore and build an intuition of how these codewords *sound*. Specially within long, multi-event audio clips, this could lead to interesting applications, such as rapid access on the underlying acoustic events.

The field of interpretability is gradually gaining attention, specially since the recent repercussion of neural network models. Many of these neural networks provide state-of-the-art accuracy in their respective tasks, but it is difficult

to understand the inner workings of the model. In the specific case of using AudioSet embeddings, sound is embedded in 128-dimensional vectors that are also difficult to interpret. The codebook approach could provide some clarification about what these embeddings represent internally.

Figure 30: Histogram representation of the Bag-of-Features model for some audio clips, after being encoded through the proposed codebook implementation (for illustrative purposes, this codebook had a size of 16). Both upper audio clips present different encodings and would be considered very different, whereas both lower audios present extremely similar quality, and would be very closely associated (indeed, both audios are the same musical loop, where one has a higher note and the other does not).

- **Evaluating results:**

Since the audio clips in FSD are labeled according to the AudioSet ontology, they can be used as ground truth. Therefore, extrinsic evaluation methods for clustering can be used (see section 2.6.1). In the first experiment (AudioSet embeddings over the FSD dataset), some extrinsic evaluation methods were computed in order to compare the clustering accuracy between the codebook approach and the statistical mean (and also to compare the different codebook

sizes between them, and global against local codebook). These metrics were slightly favorable to statistical aggregation in a big majority of subdatasets, which help to conclude that our particular implementation of codebook encoding was not improving these particular clusterings. Since the difference on the metrics was narrow, this could also imply that using a codebook approach for an ulterior application (i.e. interpretability, retrieval, or creative applications) would not noticeably damage the clustering accuracy in many cases. In the second experiment, a custom dataset was created and labeled ("natural" vs "human" environments) with the intention of applying the same extrinsic metrics, but it was soon evident that the clusters were presenting a very different arrangement, so finally subjective evaluation was put into use to allow a less restrictive examination of the results.

In retrospective, these metrics were hard to understand and were more used throughout the development process as a guideline to recognize implementation mistakes than as a definitive foundation to assess the cluster quality, specially in the second experiment where the custom dataset was not labeled according to AudioSet ontology. The challenge about evaluating clusters is well reported in numerous bibliography [90][91].

Subjective evaluation has become a basic element throughout this thesis. In this regard, a well designed experiment involving more users could be very beneficial in the future in order to reach more scientifically significant conclusions.

- **Codebook size:**

Finding the optimal codebook size presented the same evaluation challenges as the clustering itself. Relevant bibliography selected 256-sized codebooks for similar audio encoding tasks under less diverse, single-event audio datasets [96], but it was unclear how would different sizes affect the clusterings shape. After the exposed experiments, clusters were fairly similar above 128-sized codebooks; specially on the first experiment with Audioset embedded FSD, this fact could be confirmed programmatically by using the mentioned ex-

trinsic evaluation metrics to compare the different accuracies. On the second experiment, the different codebook sizes were explored subjectively with the web-visualization tool.

Under this vague conclusions, computing performance stood up as a decisive factor of the ideal codebook size. As exposed in the Results chapter, computing time for the codebook can become an issue when dealing with big codebook sizes and relatively large amounts of data(frames) for the Bag-of-Features and codebook generation. As such, 256-sized codebook seems like a trustworthy compromise.

- **Global vs local codebook:**

Under this thesis experience, more experimentation on different datasets needs to be performed in order to acquire a better intuition about the advantages and disadvantages of both local against global codebook approach in a dataset with subsets such as FSD. Obviously, within a single dataset such as our custom dataset, local and global codebook are equivalent as they are generated from the same pool of audio frames.

The advantage of the global codebook is that even if its more expensive computationally (it will potentially use all available data on FSD) it only needs to be pre-trained once, and it can be used to encode any incoming input vector afterwards. Therefore, such a codebook could be trained using a powerful computer, and then exported as a look-up table. The disadvantage would be that it is not specialised in a narrowed dataset, which could lead to excessive and trivial generalization for certain applications (for example, within a bird call dataset, maybe a global codebook would categorize all frames into too few codewords).

On the other side, local codebook deals with potentially less data. Therefore it can be computationally lighter, although as seen in the second experiment the computation time will ultimately depend on the codebook size and the input pool of frames (and their dimensionality). Hypothetically, the main advantage of a local codebook would be its specialization on certain sound

events or specific datasets, although this could not be confirmed with the evaluation metrics on the first experiment, where there was not a clear trend on whether local or global codebooks show better accuracy on FSD subsets.

- **Computing performance:**

Computing time performance turned out to be an issue in our current pipeline. This is not an entire surprise, as the focus was put on building a working model that could serve in the experiments, and computing performance was a low priority. In a production environment such as Freesound, a less naive implementation would be required.

In any case, while the global codebook could still be pre-trained offline and be used to encode any incoming input vectors in real-time, it is hard to conceive that with the current implementation, local codebook approach is practical. The local codebook is designed to be computed within a given dataset (which could be, for instance, a real-time result of a search query in Freesound). As presented in the second experiment, with only 150 (longer) input vectors, it could take 7 hours for a laptop to compute a 1000-sized codebook when dealing with very big pool of audio frames (more than 200k frames with MFCC), as the k-means execution for the codebook generation became highly expensive.

Several improvements on computing performance could be surely implemented. Maybe an hybrid solution could be to store a few pre-computed codebooks (trained on music, field recordings, percussion, human voice, all the previous, etc), but it is unclear how such a system would automatically select the most suitable pre-trained codebook in order to encode a given collection.

- **Codebook vs statistical aggregation:**

Specially when dealing with AudioSet embeddings in short, potentially single-event sounds, the codebook performance was overall less good than with statistical aggregation (in this particular case, only using the mean over each feature). Under the light of this results, this makes statistical aggregation a better solution since it is simpler to code and compute. However, under cer-

tain applications such as providing interpretability (by using histograms of the sounds to see and sonify the underlying codewords) or creative sound retrieval applications, codebook still remains a valid option as it might retain the building blocks of a multi-event audio clips.

- **Natural Language Processing:**

Besides data compression, the big potential of the codebook approach lays on the ability to apply NLP techniques on the encoded input vectors. This also could open the door to boundless creative applications.

While applying TF-IDF to the encoded vectors seems a reasonable idea and has been implemented in other fields, it is hard to confirm if there it provided an improvement in the clustering quality. Both evaluation metrics and subjective cluster exploration were not conclusive during development time. A deeper analysis is needed in order to assess if downgrading the most common codewords across the dataset is really helpful. In any case, TF-IDF was chosen as an easy to understand, classic, and relatively fast NLP technique. Now that the modular architecture of the code is implemented, it would not be a hard task to try out how different NLP models affect the clustering results.

An well-known disadvantage of both the bag-of-features/histogram or the TF-IDF normalization is that there is no inference of semantic relationship between the codewords. With this techniques, an input vector will be represented by its fundamental codewords, but a similar vector that might contain neighbouring codewords could be considered as very different (each word is presented independently). This might be problematic and not representative of the underlying patterns in the dataset. Another characteristic for these Bag-of-Words methods is that sequential temporality is lost, but this same temporality loss occurs when performing statistical aggregation.

In this regard, in future work it would be very interesting to use Word2Vec or any other neural network model, as these methods have shown the promising capability of discovering semantic relationships between the words in a corpus. It needs to be analysed if there is a possibility of computing these embeddings

in real time (probably a large dataset of encoded vectors is needed, along with heavy computational resources). Otherwise, they could be computed offline (on a big dataset of encoded vectors with a global codebook) thus codewords could benefit of this high-dimensional, more semantic embeddings.

5.1 Conclusions

This thesis originated under the research question of whether the codebook approach can enhance clustering quality, specially when dealing with multi-event, diverse sound datasets such as the ones potentially found in Freesound. Besides offering curated background based on academic literature, a modular processing pipeline written in Python is delivered. The codebase is modular enough to allow the usage of different Natural Language Processing strategies, and also different clustering techniques. Since the code is open-sourced, it can contribute to future developments upon the presented ideas.

In order to experiment with this codebase, Freesound Datasets and a brand new custom dataset of multi-event, diverse acoustic scenes were evaluated. Also, high-level feature extractors such as AudioSet embeddings and low-level MFCCs are applied and compared. While the presented results don't present any improvement of the codebook approach on the resulting clustering, several points of interest and future research ideas have been offered in this Discussion chapter.

Even if the results didn't surpass the current statistical aggregation implementation, I personally found interesting insights when dealing with the codebook approach. I still think this methodology can be useful in future projects regarding interpretability. Even so, my personal interest leans towards future research in creative endeavours. I think the codebook can empower applications that aim to find connections within different audio sources, and create regions of meaning were small sonic patterns are captured. I believe the exploration and retrieval of this connections and regions can engage a compelling artistic reward.

As a master student, I couldn't help favouring learning and experimentation over

accuracy on the results. However, researching in the academic way has also been a rewarding training process, specially about how to properly document experiments and how to curate a relevant bibliography. I also learned about the scientific mindset: curious and creative, yet rigorous, accurate and less biased.

My personal view is that the Natural Language Processing step can be also determining in future experiments, as I find the encoding capabilities of the codebook approach very thought-provoking. Basically, this allows any signal to be interpreted as a sequence of codewords, and therefore be processed analogous to a text. As it is well known, NLP field has made remarkable improvements that I am eager to test in future experiments with encoded vectors. Using TF-IDF was a good idea to present a processing pipeline due to its simplicity and computational lightness, but more sophisticated neural network embeddings (following the Word2Vec trend) could provide much more semantic results. This semantic enhancement could have an impact on processing similarities between multi-event audio clips, and potentially benefiting the resulting clusterings.

As pointed out in 1913 by the psychologist Wolfgang Köhler: "Each science has a sort of attic into which things are almost automatically pushed that cannot be used at the moment, that do not quite fit... We are constantly putting aside, unused, a wealth of valuable material that leads to the blocking of scientific progress"[102]. It is a healthy endeavour to reexamine old concepts under new circumstances. The codebook approach is a classical technique that can shine under this new light of Natural Language Processing and neural networks embeddings. It is my hope that the future reader will find interest in the concepts here exposed, and that many fruitful results will come regarding automatic *word* learning analogies.

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